

TECHNOLOGY WILL NOT CHANGE ANYTHING: HEALTHCARE WORKERS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS TECHNOLOGICAL CHANGE IN INDONESIA

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Abstract:

Background: Technology plays a fundamental role in the development of the quality of health services, but its application in health care facilities depends on the attitude of health professions to changes in technology. Therefore, studying the attitudes of medical professions relative to non-medical professions is fundamental. **Aims and Objectives:** To evaluate the attitude of medical and non-medical professions about technological change. **Materials and Methods:** This descriptive cross-sectional study involved employees of 11 hospitals in Bogor, Indonesia. It was carried out in January 2022. A convenience sampling method was used in selecting the participants for this study. Information on profession characteristics and attitudes toward technological change were collected through a structured self-administered questionnaire. **Results:** A total of 100 employees, half medical and half non-medical were targeted. Medical professions were found to be more pessimistic about the improvement in their work condition (3.84 vs 3.96, $p < 0.100$) and personal achievements (2.88 vs 3.16, $p < 0.100$) from the technological changes, compared to non-medical professions. Medical professions also believe that changes in technology will decrease employee willingness to work hard (2.42 vs 2.78, $p < 0.05$). However, they also believe that the technology will bring more security to their job compared to non-medical professions (3.70 vs 3.44, $p < 0.100$). **Conclusion:** Medical professions in Indonesian hospitals have unfavourable attitudes toward the ability of new technology to change their career and work conditions and generally the human productivity effect of the technology. Human resource development programs should be enhanced in these aspects.

Keywords: Attitude, Technological Change, Medical Professions, Indonesian Hospitals.

Introduction

Technological changes in the health sector are a necessity in the future. However, technological change in the health sector faces many challenges and complexities both at the diffusion and implementation stages.¹ Technology in the health sector increasingly demands renegotiation of work procedures and encourages interdependence between health workers.² This does not yet include the need to understand, develop and know appropriate profession behavior in dealing with new technologies.³ This has resulted in the attitude of health workers, including medical personnel, to changes in technology being relatively low. Whereas individual attitudes are very important to ensure the success of technological change interventions in an organization.^{4, 5}

Efforts to improve these attitudes require a more detailed understanding of what aspects of attitudes to technological change need to be improved specifically in the medical field and which need to be addressed with a general managerial approach. Indeed, it is not yet known whether the attitude of medical personnel is a general attitude or specific to their profession.

There have been no studies comparing attitudes to technological change between general staff and medical staff of a health care institution. This is partly due to research involving the attitude variable using measurements based on the theory of planned behavior which are general and unidimensional.⁶ In addition, studies generally only focus on health professions, not including other personnel who also work in health care facilities without a medical background such as security or admin.^{7,8}

Knowledge of the attitude characteristics of medical personnel is important to understand the special characteristics of the medical profession compared to other professions in dealing with technological changes. Given this need, this study tries to determine whether there are differences in attitudes towards technological change between medical and non-medical personnel. This study also tries to examine in what dimensions these differences arise using the multidimensional attitude variable towards technological change from Gurtoo and Tripathy.⁹

Method

We use Gurtoo and Tripathy's questionnaire to measure attitudes toward technological change and was used to measure the attitudes of medical and non-medical personnel from eleven hospitals in Indonesia.⁹ We chose this questionnaire to allow a more detailed diagnosis and comparison of the respondent's attitude data. The questionnaire consists of 25 items measured on a Likert scale from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). All items are grouped into dimensions of personal comfort, change as a challenge, uncertainty regarding work, output, control of the job, freedom on the job, and work satisfaction.

We surveyed 11 hospitals in Bogor in January 2022 to understand the attitudes of medical and non-medical personnel in these hospitals regarding technological changes. The survey asked for input from medical and non-medical personnel in a 50:50 proportion with a total sample of 100 people. Samples were taken by convenience sampling method with the number of samples per hospital not determined from the start. One hospital only gave one respondent while one hospital gave the most respondents as many as 23 respondents. Participating hospitals include Bogor Red Cross Hospital, Anisa Hospital, Budi Asih Hospital, Ciawi Hospital, IntanHusada Hospital, Juliana Hospital, Medirossa Hospital, Melania Hospital, Cisarua Lung Hospital, Salak Hospital, and Bogor Government Hospital.

Data analysis was carried out using descriptive analysis and independent samples t-test. This analysis is used to determine the distribution of respondents' answers and the level of significance of differences in respondents' answers with medical and non-medical professions. The medical professions included in this research are nutritionist, pharmacy, chief nurse, and nurse. Non-medical professions include front office, office clerks, and security.

Results

Questionnaires were collected and responses were analyzed to evaluate demographic data and attitudes towards technological change from all 100 participants. Demographic data are shown in Table 1. Only four numbers of participants were from government hospitals and 96 participants were from ten private hospitals. In this study, half of the respondents have a medical profession and another half from a non-medical profession. Among the medical staff, a total of 11, 11, 8, and 20 participants were nutritionists, pharmacists, chief nurses, and nurses respectively. Around 13 non-medical participants were front office (administration), 13 participants were office clerks, and the rest 24 are security officers.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics (n = 100)

1	Number
Type of Hospital	
Government	4
Private	96
Profession	
Medical	50
Non-medical	50
Medical profession	
Nutritionist	11
Pharmacy	11
Chief of nurse	8
Nurse Staff	20
Non-medical profession	
Front office	13
Office clerks	13
Security officers	24

The prevalence of attitude parameters among the participants is shown in Table 2. As we could see, the overall attitude between non-medical and medical professions is not significantly different. Also, there are many insignificant differences between non-medical and medical profession answers. However, for the personal comfort dimension, non-medical professions have a higher attitude than the medical profession. This is observed in two aspects: the belief that changes in technology will improve their conditions of work (3.96 vs 3.84) and the belief that changes in technology will help them to speed up their achievements (3.16 vs 2.88). Somehow, medical professions seem more pessimistic about their work improvement and personal achievement after the introduction of new technology at the hospital.

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of Attitude among the participants, n = 100

Variables		Non-medical	Medical	p-value
Personal Comfort		3.58 (.16)	3.56 (.15)	.517
1	I believe that changes in technology at the workplace will arouse my interest	3.94 (.31)	4.02 (.24)	.159
2	I believe that changes in technology at the workplace lead to improved conditions of work.	3.96 (.34)	3.84 (.37)	.098†
3	I believe that changes in technology in the workplace will allow me to add to my skills through training.	3.60 (.64)	3.76 (.47)	.159
4	I believe that changes in technology at the workplace will help me speed up my achievements.	3.16 (.79)	2.88 (.77)	.077†
5	I believe that changes in technology at the workplace will change the nature of my job for the worse. (r)	3.32 (.65)	3.52 (.58)	.109
6	I believe that changes in technology at the workplace will be a source of challenge for me	3.64 (.59)	3.44 (.88)	.188
7	I believe that changes in technology at the workplace will lead to an increase in others' expectations of me. (r)	3.00 (.64)	3.08 (.77)	.576
8	I believe that changes in technology in the workplace will improve the quality of my relationship with management.	4.02 (.37)	3.94 (.31)	.252
Change as a Challenge		4.04 (.37)	4.09 (.39)	.548
9	I believe that changes in technology at the workplace will increase my feeling of responsibility.	3.90 (.50)	3.94 (.62)	.724
10	I believes that changes in technology at the workplace will increase my commitment to work.	3.96 (.49)	4.08 (.44)	.204
11	I believes that changes in technology at the workplace will represent progress.	4.28 (.81)	4.26 (.78)	.900
Uncertainty Regarding Work		2.65 (.28)	2.67 (.35)	.677
12	I believes that changes in technology at the workplace bring in complicated situations in the workplace. (r)	2.18 (.62)	2.06 (.71)	.378
13	I believe that changes in technology at the workplace mean more job security for me.	3.44 (.76)	3.70 (.70)	.080†
14	I believes that changes in technology at the workplace will decrease my scope of work. (r)	2.32 (.58)	2.26 (.69)	.642
Output		3.57 (.60)	3.67 (.57)	.367
15	I believe that changes in technology at the workplace will save time and effort	3.14 (.98)	3.38 (.98)	.228
16	I believes that changes in technology at the workplace lead to an increase in productivity.	4.32 (.68)	4.18 (.56)	.265
17	I believes that changes in technology at the workplace will bring opportunities to earn more money.	3.24 (.91)	3.46 (.83)	.213

Variables		Non-medical	Medical	p-value
Control of the Job		3.23 (.34)	3.19 (.23)	.557
18	I believe that changes in technology at the workplace will lead to a loss of direct control over my work. (r)	2.74 (.94)	2.62 (.72)	.478
19	I believe that changes in technology at the workplace are a wasteful exercise.(r)	3.88 (.52)	3.98 (.14)	.193
20	I believe that changes in technology at the workplace will not increase my workload.	2.44 (.54)	2.40 (.53)	.711
21	I believe that changes in technology at the workplace will give me a feeling of loss of status(r)	3.86 (.35)	3.78 (.50)	.361
Freedom on the Job		3.82 (.67)	3.88 (.52)	.620
22	I believe that changes in technology at the workplace lead to an easy flow of information.	4.32 (.89)	4.26 (.80)	.724
23	I believe that changes in technology at the workplace mean increased freedom in my decision-making.	3.32 (.93)	3.50 (.70)	.280
Work Satisfaction		3.41 (.43)	3.27 (.48)	.133
24	I believe that changes in technology at the workplace will decrease employee willingness to work hard. (r).	2.78 (.86)	2.42 (.78)	.032*
25	I believe that changes in technology at the workplace will increase my expectation of satisfaction from work.	4.04 (.78)	4.12 (.71)	.595
Overall Attitude Towards Technological Change		3.46 (.17)	3.45 (.13)	.982

Note: (r) reversed scoring, † significant at $p < 0.100$, * significant at $p < 0.050$

Another significant difference was observed on the second item of uncertainty regarding work dimension. Medical professions have a significantly higher attitude toward the ability of technology to increase their job security (3.70 vs 3.44). However, when asked about the impact of technology on the willingness to work hard, medical professions scored low compared to non-medical professions. Medical professions believe that technology will decrease employee willingness to work hard (2.42 vs 2.78).

In sum, the research found that medical professions feel more uncomfortable personally with the changes in technology, believe that the technology will decrease employee willingness to work hard, but also believe that the technology did not increase their job insecurity. Overall, this means that medical professions are highly conservative about the introduction of new technology at their hospitals. Non-medical professions, despite feeling more insecure about the impact of the technology on their job security, generally feel optimistic about the technology.

This does not mean that medical professions view technology will not have any benefits. The medical professions' mean scores are higher than four in the beliefs that technology will arouse their interest (4.02), increase their commitment towards work (4.08), will represent

progress (4.26), increase productivity (4.18), flowing the information easier (4.26), and increase their expectation of satisfaction from work (4.12). They just feel that the conditions of work and their achievement would not change much by the technology and people are generally lazier because of the technology. So the threat is not to their daily operational work, but their general profession.

Looking at the lowest means, both non-medical and medical professions felt that the technology possibly will increase their workload (2.44 and 2.40), will lead to a loss of direct control over their work (2.74 vs 2.62), decrease their scope of work (2.32 vs 2.26), and make the work more complicated (2.18 vs 2.06). Hence, despite the technology will bring commitment and productivity, the new technology will also increase their workload. This could be explaining why medical professions feel that technology will not improve their work conditions and personal achievement. However, the negative effect still does not hurt their satisfaction from work, apparently because the technology will increase their interest and commitment to their jobs.

Discussion

Acceptance of new technologies in the healthcare environment presents its challenges. Special attention is paid to technological change in the health sector because technological developments in this field often lead to a redefinition of the concept of health and responsibility.¹⁰ On the other hand, the medical profession is known as one of the most conservative professions and has a strong desire to preserve and preserve its profession heritage.¹¹ This shows that technological change in the medical profession is a particular challenge that is carefully critiqued, as rigorously as the procedures for using new methods or drugs in the medical field that need to go through various stages of clinical trials before they can be widely accepted by the medical community. This is especially so because it is very difficult to get a medical profession qualification while on the other hand, technological changes make what have been studied previously for years by the medical profession can quickly expire.¹²

To the best of our knowledge, our study is the first one comparing healthcare and non-healthcare workers' attitude toward technological change in similar settings. Our results showed that healthcare workers were more inclined to believe that the new technology will not bring improvement in their work conditions and personal achievements but believe that the technology will make their job more secure. Previous research notes that working conditions related to workers' burnout and the highest burnout rates among various professions are generally occupied by health workers.¹³⁻¹⁷ Viewed in this way, it's natural that new technology should not be seen as a reliever of burnout, but rather can make it worse. Medical personnel may be asked to work harder because their previous jobs have been replaced by technology. Previous studies have found that information technology and artificial intelligence have become new sources of stress for health workers.^{18,19} Burnout is also known to be associated with perceptions of personal achievement.²⁰ Due to the belief that new technology leads to burnout, it is also reasonable to find that new technology is seen as

not having an impact on individual personal achievement.²¹

We also noted a significant difference between medical and non-medical professions in terms of beliefs that changes in technology will decrease employee willingness to work hard. Medical professions believe that changes in technology will make people lazy, higher than their non-medical counterparts. This statement reflects the impact of technology on burnout because someone who experiences burnout tends to lose motivation to work hard.²² So, the view that technology will lead to a low willingness to work hard is one reflection of the belief that new technology can create burnout for health workers.

Although the view on technological change is generally pessimistic, medical professions seem to believe that the change will bring more job security to them. Technology is often a source of job insecurity because it poses a risk that workers can be replaced by technology.²³ Job security is one source of burnout so this research finds that at least, job security is not a source of burnout for health workers.²⁴ This finding is quite similar to research on military medical personnel. Research at the Naval Medical Center found that medical personnel feel high levels of burnout but have a lot of satisfaction from what they have done.²⁵

We are aware that there are some limitations to this study. We use the descriptive method and employ the questionnaire designed by Gurtoo and Tripathy to assess the attitude towards technological change.⁹ The questionnaire is less commonly used in measuring attitudes towards technological change. However, this questionnaire is multi-dimensional so it is very helpful for diagnosing problems and differences in individual attitudes towards technological change. The medical professions in our study did not include physicians and related professions because of the difficulties in collecting responses from these busy professions. Moreover, the study was based on a self-reported questionnaire. A more objective method can add value to further research. Furthermore, our study is based solely on the Indonesian population. Ideally, it would also include hospital workers from other geographic areas, as well as other cultures. This makes it impossible for us to generalize these results to the hospital worker population at a global level.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study's findings provide a preliminary overview of potential beliefs that may exist toward a change of technology in healthcare and the differences in these beliefs between medical and non-medical workers. Specifically, medical workers pointed out that their beliefs related to the perception that technology will enhance their burnout, rather than relax it. This perception makes health workers view that technology is not able to improve work performance, working conditions, and willingness to work better. This provides an opportunity for intervention for health care facilities, especially hospitals, in various efforts to reduce burnout among medical workers. Various interventions have been offered in the literature on how to reduce burnout among health workers. These steps include maintaining good communication and working relationships, especially in face-to-face moments without being mediated by technology, facilitating teamwork with clear tasks, providing mutual support and reinforcement at work, providing adequate rest and reflection, and providing

adequate working time, adjustment of work values with leadership, as well as the appreciation of the work and autonomy of medical personnel.^{26,27} These measures directly reduce burnout and indirectly improve the attitude of health workers to technological change in hospitals.

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